

Identification of maintainers and restorers for two cytoplasmic-genetic male sterile rice lines

D. Muñoz, Annual Crop Division - ICA until April 1989 (now Genetics and Plant Breeding Program of National Rice Producers Federation [FEDEARROZ]), A.A. 52772, Bogota; and L. Lasso, Palmira Valle, Colombia

To identify maintainers and restorers for CMS lines V20 A and Shan 97 A, we evaluated pollen sterility of florets located in the upper third part of the panicle before dehiscence, florets stored at 2-11°C, and their pollen grains stained with IKI.

Maintainers and restorers^a for V20 A and Zhen Shan 97 A CMS lines at National Research Center, Palmira, Colombia.

Male parent ^a	V20 A	Zhen Shan 97 A
Fortuna blanco	M	M
Fortuna morado	M	M
Inamono	M	M
Taipei 309	M	M
Cacao Pelao	M	M
Taichung 176	M	M
IRAT 13	M	M
IRAT 12	M	M
Moroberekan	M	M
Monolaya	M	M
Miramono	M	M
Palawan	M	M
Suakoko	M	M
IRAT121	M	M
IRAT124	M	M
IRAT120	M	M
IRAT122	M	PR
Colombia 1	M	PR
Rexoro	M	M
Costa Rica	PR	M
Canilla	PR	M
L-5685	PR	PR
Monorecao	PR	PR
Llanero 501	PR	PR
Tapuripa	PR	PR
Blue-Bonnet 50	PR	PR
Araure	PR	PR
Metelapuya	PR	PR
Rustic	PR	PR
Tadukan	PR	PR
Cica 7	PR	PR
Cica 4	PR	PR
L-17388	PR	R
IR262	PR	PR
Metica 1	PR	R
Oryzica 1	PR	PR
Cica 9	PR	PR
Chianung Sen Yu 23	R	PR
IR22	R	R
Campeche A 80	R	R
L-11972	R	R
Cica 8	R	PR

^aM = maintainer, PR = partial restorer, R = restorer.

Hybrids were obtained from two CMS lines crossed with 42 standard native varieties and elite breeding lines with different growth durations.

Hybrids were transplanted in rows of 16 plants each, spaced 0.30 × 0.30 m. Eight plants, three panicles per plant, and three flowers per panicle were evaluated for sterility in the fields.

Male parents of the F₁ that showed 90-100% pollen sterility were designated maintainers. Male parents showing 21-89% pollen sterility were designated partial restorers. Male parents showing 0-20% pollen sterility were designated restorers. Maintainers were more frequent than restorers (see table). ■

Yield potential

Ratooning ability of some rice cultivars and hybrids

S. Arumugachamy, P. Vivekanandan, and M. Subramanian, Agricultural Botany Department, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai 625104, Tamil Nadu, India

We assessed ratooning yield on the basis of ratooning ability and a ratoon vigor scale. Rice genotypes Bhavani, MDU3,

IET6262, IET6709, IET7552, and IET9239 and their 30 hybrids developed on diallel crosses were planted in two rows of 10 plants each at 20- × 10-cm spacing in a randomized block design replicated three times. Recommended practices were followed for both main and ratoon crops.

The main crop was cut 20 cm from the ground at physiological maturity and allowed to ratoon. Ten randomly selected plants of each parent and hybrid from each replication were used to measure regenerated tillers and ratoon yield and to estimate ratooning ability and ratoon vigor.

Ratooning ability was assessed as number of ratoon tillers regenerated from stubble. Ratoon vigor was recorded as 1 = ratoon very vigorous (basal + nodal ratoons); 5 = ratoon normal or intermediate (only basal ratoons); and 9 = ratoon very weak or few (no counting).

A composite ratooning rating was estimated:

Ratooning rating = (1 - (0.1 ratoon vigor) × (av no. ratoon tillers/plant))

All parents except MDU3 and IET9239 showed high number of regenerated tillers. The parents IET6709, IET7552, and Bhavani recorded ratoon

Ratooning ability and yield of parents and hybrids.^a Madurai, India, 1988.

Parent or cross	Regenerated tillers (no./plant)	Ratoon vigor scale	Ratoon rating	Ratoon yield (g/10 plants)
Bhavani	8.7	1	7.8	14.4
MDU3	7.5	5	3.7	12.3
IET6262	8.9	5	4.5	12.8
IET6709	10.0	1	9.0	13.6
IET7552	9.1	1	8.2	15.1
IET9239	6.4	5	3.2	11.7
Bhavani/MDU3	9.1 (8.7)	1 (1)	8.2 (7.8)	14.5 (12.5)
Bhavani/IET6262	12.3 (10.8)	1 (1)	11.1 (9.7)	16.1 (13.2)
Bhavani/IET7552	10.1 (11.4)	1 (1)	9.1 (10.3)	14.9 (16.3)
Bhavani/IET6709	11.0 (12.7)	1 (1)	9.9 (11.5)	15.4 (15.1)
Bhavani/IET9239	8.5 (8.1)	1 (1)	7.6 (7.7)	14.3 (12.8)
MDU3/IET6262	10.4 (12.3)	5 (5)	5.2 (6.2)	12.8 (13.5)
MDU3/IET6709	9.8 (11.8)	1 (1)	8.8 (10.3)	13.1 (13.7)
MDU3/IET7552	8.7 (10.4)	5 (1)	4.3 (9.4)	12.4 (15.0)
MDU3/IET9239	8.9 (7.5)	5 (5)	4.4 (3.8)	12.5 (11.9)
IET6262/IET6709	13.1 (13.2)	1 (1)	11.8 (11.9)	14.4 (15.2)
IET6262/IET7552	10.4 (12.4)	1 (1)	9.4 (11.1)	13.0 (15.1)
IET6262/IET9239	10.1 (9.3)	5 (5)	5.1 (4.7)	12.8 (12.5)
IET6709/IET7552	15.3 (14.3)	1 (1)	13.8 (12.8)	15.2 (16.8)
IET6709/IET9239	10.2 (9.3)	1 (1)	9.2 (8.4)	13.5 (12.6)
IET7552/IET9239	10.8 (7.9)	1 (5)	9.7 (4.0)	15.9 (12.0)
Mean: Parent	8.4			13.3
Hybrids	10.6			14.0
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.8			0.8

^a Figures in the parentheses are for the reciprocal cross.

vigor scale of 1 and high ratoon rating. Crosses involving IET6709 and IET7552 as one of the parents had high ratooning ability and ratoon yield. Among the hybrids, IET6709/IET7552 and its

reciprocal registered maximum tillers, with a ratoon vigor scale of 1 and with good ratoon rating; that resulted in high ratoon yield. ■

Influence of variety, irrigation, and N level on production of effective ratoon tillers

A. Palchamy, S. Purushothaman, and A. Kajagopal, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai, India

We studied the production of effective ratoon tillers in a field trial 1984-85 and 1985-86. Rice varieties Bhavani, Ponni, and IR20 were grown under normal management for the main crop. The

ratoon crops were grown with two irrigation schedules (5 cm water throughout the crop period and 5 cm water 1 d after the disappearance of ponded water) and four N levels (50, 75, 100, and 125 kg N/ha) in a split-plot design with three replications. Main crop plots were harvested separately, at 20-cm high, with one border row left on all sides.

Number of productive ratoon tillers had a direct bearing on productivity. More productive tillers/hill were recovered in the second year than in the first year (Table 1). ■

Table 1. Effect of variety, irrigation, and N level (50, 75, 100, 125 kg N/ha) on productive ratoon tillers/hill.

Treatment	Productive tillers (no./hill)									
	1984-85					1985-86				
	50	75	100	125	Mean	50	75	100	125	Mean
Bhavani	9.4	10.4	11.3	11.7	10.7	10.1	11.8	13.1	14.8	12.5
Ponni	6.6	7.6	8.0	8.8	7.7	9.7	11.0	13.0	13.9	11.9
IR20	5.2	5.5	5.6	6.7	5.8	9.9	11.0	12.4	13.4	11.7
Continuous Irrigation (C)	7.3	7.7	7.6	8.3	7.7	10.2	11.5	12.4	13.6	11.9
Intermittent Irrigation (I)	6.8	8.4	9.0	9.8	8.4	9.7	11.0	13.2	14.5	12.1
Bhavani-C	10.1	10.2	10.1	10.6	10.2	10.1	11.3	12.3	13.6	11.8
Bhavani-I	8.8	10.7	12.5	12.7	11.2	10.1	12.4	14.0	16.0	13.1
Ponni-C	6.7	7.5	7.6	8.0	7.5	9.3	11.4	12.7	13.8	11.8
Ponni-I	6.4	7.7	8.3	9.7	8.3	10.1	10.6	13.3	14.1	12.0
IR20-C	5.1	5.3	5.2	6.3	5.5	11.1	12.0	12.3	13.5	12.2
IR20-I	5.4	5.7	6.1	7.0	6.1	8.8	9.9	12.4	13.3	11.1
Mean	7.1	7.9	8.3	9.1		9.9	11.3	12.8	14.0	
Variety (V)				LSD						LSD
Irrigation				2.0						NS
V × C				NS						NS
Nitrogen (N)				NS						NS
V × Irrigation				0.8						0.8
N × V				NS						NS
N × Irrigation				NS						NS

Table 2. Productive tillers and yield of main and ratoon crops.

Variety	1984-85				1985-86			
	Tillers (no.)		Yield (t/ha)		Tillers (no.)		Yield (t/ha)	
	Main crop	Ratoon crop	Main crop	Ratoon crop	Main crop	Ratoon crop	Main crop	Ratoon crop
Bhavani	10.5	10.7	2.92	1.60	10.5	12.5	5.14	2.94
Ponni	7.2	7.7	2.49	0.96	9.2	11.9	5.33	1.25
IR20	4.5	5.8	3.83	0.32	11.2	11.7	5.57	0.314
LSD	1.5	2.0	0.400	0.073	1.1	ns	ns	0.158

During the first year, Bhavani had the most productive tillers/hill. This may have been due to higher carbohydrate content in the stubble crop and more regeneration capacity. Irrigation level and the interaction of varieties and irrigation level did not influence number of productive tillers. Tiller production under different N levels varied significantly, with an increase in productive tillers with increasing N.

The ratoon crop produced more productive tillers than the main crop both years (Table 2), perhaps because the ratoon crop produced tillers from the top as well as from the basal nodes. Almost all tillers formed in the ratoon crop bear panicles. ■

Growth and yield of rice varieties grown in deep water

A. R. Sharma and M. D. Reddy, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, India

We evaluated growth and yield of 13 promising rice lines developed at different research stations under deep water (up to 80 cm) at Cuttack. The photoperiod-sensitive, long-duration (170-180 d), tall (150-200 cm) cultivars and a local check were sown on 26 May at 400 seeds/m², 20-cm row spacing, and fertilized with 40 kg N, 9 kg P/ha in the furrow. The experiment was laid out in randomized complete block design with three replications.

Water started accumulating in the field at 7 d after emergence (DE) and increased rapidly to 40 cm at 25 DE. It reached maximum depths of 76 and 83 cm at 60 and 100 DE, respectively, then receded gradually to near zero at crop maturity.

Yields in general were low, because panicles/m² were few. Water stress at very early growth stages caused seedling death and adversely affected tillering. Tall cultivars (IET10084, IET10030, IET10029, IET10008, and IET10003) yielded more than 3 t/ha; relatively short cultivars (IET10006, IET9071, IET9017, IET11184, and local check Hathipanja) produced less than 2